

Designing an Instructional System for Physical Education Sports and Health Based On the Local Wisdom of Traditional Games of *UrangBanjar*

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Abstract—This study aims to develop a guide to designing an elementary school PE learning system based on the local wisdom of the traditional game of *urangBanjar* which is seen from the aspect of the appearance of the guide, the aspect of user impact, and the feasibility aspect of the guide. With the guide, it is hoped that it can help elementary school PE teachers to be able to design an elementary school PE learning system based on local wisdom. The method used in this research is a development method modified from the development method of Meredith D. Gall, Joyce P. Gall, Walter R. Borg, namely 1) preliminary study, 2) development, 3) testing. Testing. For individual trials conducted on 3 PE teachers, small group trials conducted on 9 elementary school PE teachers, and field trials conducted on 41 elementary school PE teachers. The instrument used in this research is a questionnaire sheet that teachers respond to. The results of the research on the trial of guidelines for designing elementary school PE learning systems based on local wisdom of traditional games *urangBanjar* showed that 1) Teachers' responses to the display aspect of the guide are categorized as high/good, 2) In the aspect of user impact, the guide is categorized as high/good based on teacher responses, 3) Categorized as high/good in the feasibility aspect based on teacher responses.

Index Terms—Design, Learning System, Local Wisdom

I. Introduction

Learning is a process of activity that aims to improve the ability to achieve certain goals. In the world of education, learning can be interpreted as an activity carried out by the teacher in a programmed manner designed to make students active in achieving learning goals. Witayasa et al., (2017: 1) revealed that learning is essentially a programmed teacher activity in instructional design to make students learn actively which emphasizes the provision of learning resources. Teachers and students in this context have their respective roles. Teachers are facilitators or providers of facilities in the learning process, while participants are the main actors in the learning process. Learning carried out by a teacher is basically a system because learning is an activity that aims, namely activities to teach students. The learning process is a series of activities involving various components, namely: objectives, content / subject matter, strategies / methods,

tools and resources and evaluation. This needs to be understood, because through understanding the learning system, at least the teacher will understand the learning objectives or expected results, the process of learning activities that must be carried out, the utilization of each component in the activity process to achieve the goals to be achieved and how to know the success of this achievement. A good learning process will produce good results. A good process is the result of a good design and is carried out correctly and precisely by good (qualified) teachers. A good design is certainly prepared by teachers who master the problem carefully. The ability to plan appropriately requires a good understanding of the problem and being able to see the picture to achieve the expected goals. Therefore, a physical education teacher is required to be able to design the learning process and at the same time implement it in the field. That is a professional teacher who has pedagogical competence in managing student learning, a teacher whose profession is a teacher.

Based on temporary observations made, teachers have actually made efforts to design learning systems but these efforts do not seem to have been carried out in the right way, model and system to the maximum. This fact can be seen from most of the learning designs that teachers have made are based on the syllabus, but it seems that the design is designed not based on identifying the innate abilities that students already have in advance. In addition, the design of specific learning objectives, evaluation design, learning strategies, selection and development of learning materials do not seem to have been carried out in a system and manner that should be learning strategies designed by teachers are only limited to requiring mastery of one or two learning domains. As a result, teachers do not have a good learning system design to be applied in learning that is fun and centered on learner learning activities. In the learning process, how each learner can perform is the most important variable in the design of motor skill learning in physical education. Appropriate learner practice is practice that is neither too difficult nor too easy. Designing motor learning that is difficult will result in learners who do not have the skills not trying very

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often and activities that are too difficult will impact on skill and attitude development. Difficult practices should be planned according to learners' ability levels so that all can participate in the activity. In fact, most physical education activities are not too difficult if the lesson is based on analyzing the prerequisite skills for the next change in practice task (Silverman & Mercier, 2015: 152).

Physical education sports and health is one of the subjects in elementary school which is an integral part of education. It is simply explained that physical education is a process of learning to move and learning through movement so that this is the difficulty faced by teachers in designing learning according to what is expected in the curriculum. The inability of teachers to design a quality learning system as described is caused by several factors, one of which is the lack of available teaching materials/learning resources that do not seem to be able to be guided and applied directly and well by teachers. In addition, the model presented has not been accompanied by real examples in learning as desired by the teacher. Thus, the available learning materials do not seem to be able to be used optimally. This is also supported by the ability of teachers who do not seem to have adequate knowledge about learning design models and skills in designing learning systems correctly.

From the description above, it is necessary to conduct research and development in order to produce a guide to designing elementary school PE learning systems based on local wisdom of traditional games of *wrang* Banjar that can be used by teachers easily, so that teachers can design elementary school PE learning systems based on local wisdom. This learning design contains physical elements (physical fitness both strength, speed, flexibility, and endurance), psychomotor elements (habitual movements, complex movements, and adjustments to movement patterns), cognitive elements (understanding, application, and analysis), and affective elements (honesty, responsibility, hard work, cooperation, perseverance, discipline, togetherness, and friendship).

II. Theoretical Foundation

A. Physical Education Sports and Health

Physical education is a process that aims to educate a person, develop his physical abilities, acquire skills and knowledge in the field of physical and sports to form a mature human being comprehensively and physically healthy. (Xolmirzaevich, 2022: 88). The overall goal of physical education is to develop physical fitness is to build and shape individual strength through the development of the body's organic system. The result is to be able to adapt, rest, and resist fatigue. This goal is based on the fact that individuals will be more active, show better performance, and be healthy if the body's organic system is developed properly and according to its function Krotee and Harfield (1979) in Bucher & Krotee (2002: 32) state that aspects related to fitness are cardiovascular and cardiorespiratory efficiency and endurance, namely

body composition: muscle strength, endurance, power, flexibility, and relaxation. As revealed by Koka and Hagger (2010) in Ada et al (2018: 115) that physical education at school has been recognized as one of the most important things to acquire lifelong habits in physical activity. With physical education, students are expected to understand and appreciate the value of physical education in relation to a healthy active lifestyle and move at an optimal level of physical fitness through movement activities.

B. Learning System Design

A good learning design is likened to a system consisting of an arrangement of various resources and procedures to drive learning. According to Dick et al., (2015: 1) "A system is technically a set of interrelated parts, all of which work together" Why is it said to be a system because the components are interrelated and interact with each other to achieve an optimal expected result in accordance with the predetermined objectives. The learning design should go through a process using a system approach that frames each instructional component systemically and systematically (Suparman, 2014: 85). It is said to be a system because learning is an activity that aims to teach students. Learning through a process that is a series of activities involving many components that interact, interdependence and integration. The goal is to ensure quality, effective, efficient and enjoyable instruction (Ashfaq, 2016:5). Due to the distinct and complex nature of the instructional design process and practice, the field of instructional design seems to be evolving more specifically (Sharif & Cho, 2015:74). Based on that assumption, that we need to learn and teach principles that are more in line with instructional design (York & Ertmer, 2016:189) Therefore, we must first understand the concept and nature of learning system design.

C. Local Wisdom

Local wisdom in its definition consists of two words: wisdom and local. Wisdom is a trait inherent in a person's character, which means wise and prudent. Meanwhile, local is the condition of a place or locality. Kons, Steinbach, & Kivestu (2016: 159) reveal that local wisdom is a local tradition in which the use of language, songs, customs, folklore and games and other traditional elements of an area that provide social experience. The form of local wisdom can be interpreted as a representation of various forms of cultural heritage that still exist today (Sudirman, Mellawaty, Yaniwati, & Indrawan, 2020: 92). Kaimuddin Haris, Syahbudin, & Yunus, (2019: 41) say local wisdom is the ability to deal with a foreign culture that affects them. Another geographical condition of South Kalimantan Province is that there are many swamps and rivers, while the largest tribe in South Kalimantan Province is the Banjar tribe (Ramdiah, Abidinsyah, Royani, Husamah, & Fauzi, 2020: 640) Urang Banjar is a population that inhabits the Banjar kingdom which was established in the

16th century. From several sources obtained that some traditional games of *urang*Banjar are truly original from Banjar. Some of the following traditional games of Urang Banjar have begun to be unfamiliar and even unknown to children, namely: *babanga, bacirak, badadamaran, bagasing, bagual, bagugulungan, bahasinan, baintingan, bajajangkirikan, bajajaran, bajujukungan, bajujungatan, bakakapalan, bakalikir, bakarar, bakalayangan, bakakatikan, bakujur, balogo, bapidak, basamsaman, basimban, basusumpitan, batapakan, batitimbakan, baulasan, baupauan, babintih, babulanan, baburungan, bacit, badurit, bagimpar, bagum, balubuk, basaungkalatau, basusumpitan, batatimbulanilung, bausutan, isutjarat, tandikpelanduk, and bapatakan* (Usman, 2000: 3). Based on the definition of local wisdom that has been presented, it can be concluded that local wisdom is everything that is the potential of an area as well as the results of human thought and human work that contains wise and wise values and is passed down from generation to generation so that it characterizes the area.

III. Research Method

The procedure or development steps are modified from Meredith D. Gall, Joyce P. Gall, and Walter R. Borg, namely 1) preliminary study, 2) development, 3) trial. The data needed in this development research is divided into two parts, namely data for developing teacher guides and data for developing local wisdom-based learning designs.

IV. Results and Discussion

Collecting data about the feasibility of teacher guides to assist in making learning designs using questionnaires to teachers. Table 1 Feasibility of the Teacher's Guide to Creating a Local Wisdom-Based PE Learning Program Plan Based on Small Group Test Teacher Questionnaires.

Feasibility data for teacher guides can be seen in Table 1. The Table above shows that the level of feasibility of the teacher's guide for the clarity component of the teacher's guide is in a high category with a percentage of 55.56% based on teacher responses related to the clarity of the appearance of the teacher's guide, the attractiveness of the teacher's guide so that it is different from other learning guides, the teacher's guide is neat so that it is easy to use, the appearance of the teacher's guide is clear and attractive and easy to use, the use of fonts in the teacher's guide is easy and clear to read, the use of font size in the teacher's guide is easy and clear to read, consistent use of font type and size in the teacher's guide, the overall text in this teacher's guide is neat and clear, the illustration photos in this teacher's guide are clear and interesting, this teacher's guide is simple and not excessive, and the composition in this teacher's guide is neatly and clearly organized.

For the user impact of the teacher's guide in the high category with a percentage of 55.56% based on teacher responses, among others, that the teacher's guide provides

knowledge and understanding, the material presented is relevant to the needs of teachers to design lessons, the examples presented in the guide can guide the implementation of demonstrations, the teacher's guide fosters interest and motivation to read, the teacher's guide fosters interest in learning independently and in groups, and the teacher's guide fosters interest and motivation in learning to use it.

In the feasibility component, the teacher's guide is in a high category with a percentage of 66.67 based on teacher responses related to the teacher's guide worthy of being used as a learning resource, material about the learning design development model is easy to understand, material about identifying and determining general learning objectives is easy to understand, material about identifying learners' initial abilities is easy to understand, material about writing specific learning objectives is easy to understand, material about developing benchmark assessments is easy to understand, material about developing learning strategies is easy to understand, The material on designing formative and summative evaluations is easy to understand, the materials in the teacher's guide are in accordance with the learning objectives, the performance instructions and examples in the material are easy to understand, the summary in the teacher's guide is easy to understand, the use of teacher's guides is important for learning, the use of teacher's guides can enrich learning resources, the use of teacher's guides can learn to design learning more effectively, the use of guides can be used without being limited by space and time, the use of guides can foster skills in learning, the use of guides is feasible and can stimulate critical and creative thinking, the use of guides can foster independence in learning, the use of guides can stimulate to interact with fellow professionals.

The validation of the guide to designing elementary school PE learning based on the local wisdom of the traditional game of *urang*Banjar is in the high category but there are notes from teachers about the shortcomings in this guide so that it needs improvement and revision in the aspect of clarity of the guide related to the appearance of the guide is made to be more attractive and different from other guides, the size of the letters so that the guide is easy and clear to read. In the aspect of impact on users, improvements and revisions were made for the examples presented in the guide so that they could be more easily understood for performance. For the feasibility aspect of the guide, improvements and revisions were also made to the material on designing formative and summative evaluations to make it easy to understand. After making improvements and revisions to the teacher's guide, it will be continued and used for field trials. The results can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2 shows the level of feasibility of the teacher's guide for the clarity component. The teacher's guide is in a high category with a percentage of 65.85% based on teacher responses related to the clarity of the appearance of the teacher's guide, the attractiveness of the teacher's guide so that it is different from other learning guides,

TABLE I
Small Group Test Teacher Questionnaires

Component	Teachers				
	Very high (%)	High (%)	Medium (%)	Low (%)	Very low (%)
Clarity	22.22	55.56	22.22	-	-
Impact	33.33	55.56	11.11	-	-
Feasibility	11.11	66.67	22.22	-	-
Total	-	-	-	-	-

TABLE II
Field trials Test Teacher Questionnaires

Component	Teachers				
	Very high (%)	High (%)	Medium (%)	Low (%)	Very low (%)
Clarity	31.71	65.85	2.44	-	-
Impact	9.76	87.8	2.44	-	-
Feasibility	36.59	63.41	-	-	-
Total	-	-	-	-	-

the teacher's guide is neat so that it is easy to use, the appearance of the teacher's guide is clear and attractive and easy to use, the use of fonts in the teacher's guide is easy and clear to read, The use of font size in the teacher's guide is easy and clear to read, consistent in the use of font type and size in the teacher's guide, the overall text in this teacher's guide is neat and clear, the illustration photos in this teacher's guide are clear and interesting, this teacher's guide is simple and not excessive, and the composition in this teacher's guide is neatly and clearly organized.

For the user impact of the teacher's guide in the high category with a percentage of 87.80% for the user impact component of the teacher's guide based on teacher responses, among others, that the teacher's guide provides knowledge and understanding, the material presented is relevant to the needs of teachers to design lessons, the examples presented in the guide can guide the implementation of demonstrations, the teacher's guide fosters interest and motivation to read, the teacher's guide fosters interest in learning independently and in groups, and the teacher's guide fosters interest and motivation in learning to use it.

In the feasibility component, the teacher's guide is in a high category with a percentage of 63.41% based on teacher responses related to the teacher's guide worthy of being used as a learning resource, material about the learning design development model is easy to understand, material about the learning design development model is easy to understand, material about identifying and determining general learning objectives is easy to understand, material about learning analysis is easy to understand, material about identifying learners' initial abilities is easy to understand, material about writing specific learning objectives is easy to understand, material about developing benchmark assessments is easy to understand, material about developing learning strategies is easy to understand, material about designing formative and summative evaluations is easy to understand, the materials in the teacher's guide are in accordance with the learning objectives, the performance instructions and

examples in the material are easy to understand, the summary in the teacher's guide is easy to understand, the use of teacher guides is important for learning, the use of teacher guides can enrich learning resources, the use of teacher guides can learn to design learning more effectively, the use of guides can be used without being limited by space and time, the use of guides can foster skills in learning, the use of guides is feasible and can stimulate critical and creative thinking, the use of guides can foster independence in learning, the use of guides can stimulate interaction with fellow professionals.

V. Results and discussion

The guide to designing an elementary school PE learning system based on the local wisdom of *urang* Banjar traditional games, both in terms of the clarity of the guide, was identified as being categorized as high or having good quality according to teacher responses. In the aspect of user impact, it was identified to be categorized as high or having good quality according to teacher responses. For the feasibility aspect, the identified guide is categorized as high or has good quality according to teacher responses. Designing learning is not an easy thing so that the learning that is carried out has meaning in accordance with educational objectives, therefore, making learning design basically determines learning objectives through indications, describes learning materials, arranges learning steps, and determines learning evaluation. Physical education sports and health in elementary schools expects this special product of local wisdom-based learning design to provide an overview of development for physical fitness and development for movement skills so that, in the preparation of learning objectives and indications, elementary school PE teachers need to consider the level of psychomotor aspects to achieve optimal learner potential.

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